

**CHECKING THE OPINIONS AND KNOWLEDGE OF THE POPULATION
ABOUT THE NEGATIVE EFFECTS OF TOBACCO PRODUCTS ON THE
NATURE, ANALYSIS AND ASSESSMENT OF THE ECOLOGICAL CULTURE**

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Abstract. This thesis highlights the results of the investigation of the opinion and knowledge of the population about the harmful habit - the consumption of tobacco products (cigarettes) and its harm to nature, which has been rapidly increasing among the population in recent years. The research was carried out in the form of a questionnaire, for five days, using the "Telegram" messenger. According to the results of the survey, 248 people read the questionnaires, but more than 118 people (48 %) actively answered the questions.

Key words: Cigarette products, fake food, ocean pollution, water pollution, soil pollution, air pollution, carcinogenic substances, human health, damage to nature, ecological behavior, ecological culture.

Introduction

The ever-increasing number of smokers is nothing new. More information about the negative effects of tobacco on human health has been proven by long-term research, but the extent of its negative effects on nature, flora and fauna, soil, air and water environment has also increased. The number of deaths caused by smoking takes the lead in the world. It was determined that more than half of tobacco smokers die as a result of serious consequences caused by its consumption [1]. Harmful smoke produced by smoking poisons the atmosphere. Cigarette residues fall into water and air in various ways, damaging them with nicotine, pesticide residues and fertilizers [2]. An estimated 766,571 metric tons of cigarette butts make their way into the environment every year. Cigarettes make up 30-40% of all household waste collected from cities and coasts. 75% of smokers, after using a cigarette, throw its residue out of the car and throw it on

the ground [3]. The increase in the number of smokers is the reason for the increase in the number of companies that grow them, and as a result, the natural forests are cut down (deforestation) [4]. Animals (for example, birds, and fish) mistake cigarette residues for food and eat them, which causes toxic substances to enter the body [5]. Below are the results of a small research in order to determine people's knowledge about the harm caused by cigarettes and its residues to nature and the human body, and to study their attitudes and behavior.

Research Methodology

Below are the results of a small research conducted to check and analyze people's knowledge about cigarette products, their negative effects on nature and human health. The research was conducted in the form of a questionnaire. "Telegram" messenger was used for this purpose. The research was conducted anonymously for 5 days, consisting of 5 questions, two or three different answers, and 248 people got acquainted with the electronic questionnaire directly, of which 48% (118 people) answered the questions. 52% (130 people) of those who read the questionnaire did not answer the questionnaire questions [Figure 1].

Questionnaire questions were made as follows: 1. Do you smoke cigarettes? 2. Do you know that cigarette residues thrown on the earth and in water look like food for animals? 3. Do you believe that cigarette residues have been found in the stomachs of aquatic animals and birds? 4. Did you know that tobacco smoke contains thousands of tons of carcinogens, toxins and greenhouse gases? 5. Do you know that tobacco smoke is more harmful to those around you than the smoker?

Figure 1. Inactive (52 %) and active (48 %)

Results and Discussion

Answers to survey questions were also put into diagrams and analyzed. "Do you smoke?" 130 people answered the first question called, and the results were represented by the following diagram (Figure 2).

Figure 2.

The second question that is, "Do you know that cigarette residues thrown on the earth and in water appear as food for animals?" 123 people answered the question and the answers can be found in the diagram below (Figure 3).

Figure 3.

The third question that is, "Do you believe that cigarette residues have been found in the stomachs of aquatic animals and birds?" 121 people answered the question and the results of the analysis are represented by diagram 3 (Figure 4).

Figure 4.

The fourth question of the anonymous survey, that is, "Do you know that there are thousands of tons of carcinogens, toxic substances and greenhouse gases in the waste of tobacco smoke?" 115 people answered the question, and these answers are represented by Figure 5 (Figure 5).

Figure 5.

The fifth question of the anonymous survey, "Do you know that tobacco smoke is more harmful to those around you than the smoker?" 101 people answered the question, and the results are illustrated by Figure 6 (Figure 6).

Figure 6.

Conclusion

The number of activists participating in the survey is close to 50% (48%), which shows that the population is not indifferent to cigarette smokers and the negative effects of smoking on people and the environment. The number of activists participating in the survey is close to 50% (48%), which shows that the population is not indifferent to cigarette smokers and the negative effects of smoking on people and the environment. According to the results of the first question of the survey, most of the respondents (77%) do not smoke, so it can be concluded that the population does not have a high number of smokers. Most of the survey respondents (63%) do not know that cigarette residues thrown into the environment (into water, on the surface of the soil) can be used as feed for animals, which shows that knowledge about ecology is lacking. 48% (the majority) of the respondents answered Yes, 22% No, and 30% I don't know to the next question asking whether they believe that cigarette residues are found in the stomachs of aquatic animals and birds. It was found that the majority of respondents (64%) are aware that tobacco products contain many harmful substances, while the majority of the people (94%) know that the people around them are more harmed than the tobacco user. As a conclusion, it can be said that the majority of the population has sufficient knowledge, skills and qualifications about the harm of tobacco and its products.

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